

Production of large SiC_f/SiC tubular-shaped samples through Microwave-assisted Chemical Vapor Infiltration

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Abstract

This contribution describes a customized approach enabling the scalability of the Microwave-assisted Chemical Vapor Infiltration (MW-CVI) technology for the production of a SiC_f/SiC tube having a diameter of 10 cm, height of 12.7 cm, wall thickness of 0.3 cm, and a starting density of 1.39 g/cm³, through a reactor enabling a multiport and multifrequency excitation around 2.45 GHz.

Comprehensive, rigorous numerical modelling of the MW-CVI loaded reactor allowed the reliable identification of the optimal frequencies combination, maximizing the process energy efficiency and heating pattern uniformity. A total MW power of 4.5 – 5 kW was distributed among the three available excitation ports, achieving an unprecedented uniformity in the temperature profile of the CMC tube, in the operating temperature range of 800°C – 1000°C. The temperature distribution showed a strong dependence on the sample density. After 50 hours of MW-CVI, the SiC_f/SiC tube was successfully densified, reaching a density of 1.85 g/cm³ with an average deposition rate of 0.76 g/h. X-ray computed tomography results confirmed the achievement of a controlled SiC matrix densification front, avoiding conventional crusting issues and showing a homogeneous porosity reduction in the CMC sample volume.

The obtained results pave the way for a wider and more efficient application of MW-assisted processes in high-temperature industrial applications, contributing to the development of alternative greener technologies.

Keywords

Microwave-assisted material processing, Ceramic Matrix Composites, SiC_f/SiC, Chemical Vapor Infiltration, Multifrequency technique

1. Introduction

The escalating problems resulting from climate change and especially the environmental impacts of anthropogenic activities are getting increasingly exponential attention. This is reflected in the “European Green Deal” [1], which clearly outlines, among the main objectives, the research and innovation on technologies that will allow an intense exploitation of renewable energy sources, improvement of energy efficiency, and development of new low-carbon technologies. One of the most promising avenues for addressing both energy consumption and emissions is the integration of high-performance materials, particularly in energy-intensive industries. Among them, Silicon Carbide fiber reinforced Silicon Carbide Ceramic Matrix Composites (SiC_f/SiC CMCs) have emerged as potential candidates in various strategic sectors due to their exceptional thermal, mechanical, and chemical properties [2–4]. These materials combine the high-temperature stability of ceramics with the toughness and damage tolerance of metals, making them ideal for applications such as aerospace [5–7] and energy [8,9].

In this framework, the production of SiC_f/SiC tubes with dimensions of industrial interest can pave the way in many other key sectors as Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) [10] or nuclear, where they represent one of the few options as core materials for Gen IV reactors [11]. As such, recently SiC_f/SiC tubes were also considered as candidates to replace Inconel-based superalloys, currently employed in the hottest sections of radiant tube furnaces in steelmaking applications, during the EU CEM-WAVE project [12].

For the production of large CMC tubular components, several techniques are available. Polymer Impregnation and Pyrolysis (PIP) and Liquid Silicon Infiltration (LSI) [13–15], although popular for CMCs as Carbon-fiber reinforced SiC or C-SiC matrix composites (C_f/SiC , $\text{C}_f/\text{C-SiC}$), remain less suitable for SiC_f/SiC manufacturing, in particular when a pure crystalline SiC matrix is mandatory [16]. In this framework, the PIP process does not lead to a pure SiC matrix rather to a low crystalline silicon oxycarbide (SiOC) or silicon carbonitride (SiCN) matrix [17]. Differently, the LSI process, despite its remarkably low processing times, demands expensive SiC fibers and protective interphase coatings to avoid degradation of the SiC_f/SiC composite, due to the aggressive action of molten silicon. Furthermore, the resulting composite is usually characterized by a 10-15 vol% unreacted silicon content, thus reducing its high-temperature performance [18,19].

Chemical Vapor Infiltration (CVI) offers precise control over the SiC matrix composition, enabling superior oxidation resistance and microstructural integrity critical for high-temperature applications [20–22]. However, traditional CVI faces limitations, particularly for the infiltration of complex, near-net-shape sample geometries due to surface crusting [23], thus demanding periodic

machining to reopen the external porosity [24]. The machining of curved surfaces poses additional challenges due to the brittle and anisotropic nature of ceramics, making them particularly prone to the occurrence of surface cracks, inconsistent material removal, and tolerance issues due to uneven tool contact [25,26]. Other techniques as ultrasonic vibration-assisted and rotary ultrasonic machining, which are essential for achieving precision and quality in tubular CMCs, require careful parameter optimization to prevent defects [27,28] and add further steps in the production process. Hence, despite incremental advances, the fabrication of large SiC_f/SiC tubes remains constrained to conventional CVI techniques. In general, the various production methods primarily provide tubes up to 20-30 mm in diameter for specific applications [29–31].

To overcome the limitations of the conventional CVI process, a Microwave-assisted CVI (MW-CVI) variant was proposed [32–34]. Replacing the resistive heating of the entire reaction chamber with a selective MW heating of the sample alone is expected to provide a significant gain in the energy efficiency and in the dead production times related to the reactor cooling. Moreover, the MW heating is very fast and volumetric, enabling reversal thermal gradients in the sample and thus avoiding conventional crusting issues with a consequent reduction of about one order of magnitude of the processing times (~ 100 h vs 2000 h) [35].

However, building high-temperature MW-assisted chemical reactors that are able to produce large samples of industrial interest is challenging [36,37]. The homogeneous heating of samples with dimensions comparable to or larger than the employed wavelength λ_{MW} proved very difficult, owing to the standing wave pattern of the MW radiation in the reactor. In constrained geometries, the electric field usually shows strong variations over distances larger than $\lambda_{MW}/4$, which thus represents a kind of barrier for a homogeneous heating of the sample. Moreover, reproducible operating conditions and processing can be hindered by the use of incoherent MW sources as magnetrons [38]. The situation is further complicated by the changes in the material dielectric properties with temperature, which translates to changes in the electromagnetic (EM) spectrum of the reactor [39]. Besides this, the occurrence of sparks and plasma phenomena represents a serious issue to deal with, in particular in processing conditions characterized by low gas pressures.

In comparison to standard reactors, the design of efficient MW reactors imposes a radically different perspective, in which the expected size, shape, as well as dielectric, thermal, and emission properties of the sample to be processed must be taken into account from the beginning. The MW source and excitation system represent as well key parts of the reactor, which must ensure the necessary adaptability of the operating frequency and coupled power, as requested by the variable EM spectrum of the reactor. The MW parameters should be rapidly controllable according to the

temperature distribution of the sample, considering the densification process and the possible occurrence of unexpected phenomena as hot spots and sparks.

The design of reactors for MW-assisted processing based on multimode, or overmoded, resonant cavities represents the most common choice for industrial purposes, due to the possibility of processing relatively large or complex-shaped sample volumes [40]. Common limitations of these MW applicators concern the difficult heating of large samples throughout the whole process and the prediction of the optimal MW heating parameters, providing high energy efficiency and a uniform temperature profile [41].

In recent works, we proved that the MW heating and infiltration of a material within an overmoded cavity can be numerically investigated with great accuracy, provided that the EM behavior of the reactor is properly engineered and the dielectric, thermal, and emission properties of the sample are accurately characterized as a function of the temperature [42,43]. However, the obtained results were limited to flat samples of relatively small size and limited industrial interest, leaving open the fundamental question concerning the scalability of the proposed technique to samples of large dimensions.

Aim of this work is to demonstrate that the “ $\lambda_{MW}/4$ barrier” in MW-assisted processes can be effectively lifted by combining a proper design of the reactor with a rigorous and accurate numerical modelling of the process. The reaching of this goal is supported by the results of 50 hours of densification processing of a large tubular-shaped SiC_f/SiC sample, characterized by a 4.3-fold higher volume with respect to the previous square-shaped sample geometry considered [43]. These results prove that the MW-CVI is a mature technique for the production of near-net-shape CMC components with complex geometries and dimensions of industrial interest.

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1 MW-CVI reactor description and SiC_f/SiC tubular-shaped preform properties

The MW-CVI tests were performed at the pilot plant of the joint IPCF-CNR – UNIPI laboratory, equipped by a reactor with a 3-port excitation scheme based on a 2 kW x 3 microwave Solid-State Generators (SSGs) system covering the whole 2.4 – 2.5 GHz Industrial Scientific and Medical (ISM) frequency band [44]. The design of the MW-CVI reactor was carried out to achieve a rather smooth and continuous EM spectrum characterized by high-energy efficiency heating modes in which the majority of the MW power is dissipated in the material [42].

In this work, a tubular-shaped SiC_f/SiC preform with a diameter of 10 cm, length of 12.7 cm, and wall thickness of 0.3 cm, identified as SiC_f/SiC-C2 (see **Table 1**), was considered. The preform was manufactured at the Fraunhofer ISC/Center HTL (Bayreuth, Germany) by Filament Winding process, using 3rd generation Hi-Nicalon Type S fibers (NGS Advanced Fibers Co., Ltd., Japan) coated with a tailored multilayer (BN/SiC)₃ interphase system through a wet-chemical approach, according to the methodology described in [43]. The CMC tube external borders were coated with a SiC-based slurry, whose formulation was derived from [45], to mitigate arcing issues. The open porosity and bulk density of the preform were determined by Archimedes method according to DIN EN 1389 standard. **Table 1** reports the main preform manufacturing parameters and properties.

Table 1 - SiC_f/SiC-C2 tubular preform tested by MW-CVI process with manufacturing parameters and properties

#ID sample	SiC _f /SiC-C2
<i>Roving</i>	200 tex
<i>Green body matrix</i>	Epoxy
<i>Pyrolyzed matrix</i>	Carbon
<i>Geometry [D x L x T, cm]</i>	10×12.7×0.3
<i>Starting open porosity [%vol]</i>	50.20
<i>Starting density [g/cm³]</i>	1.39

The SiC matrix densification pattern and porosity levels distribution in the sample volume post-infiltration were characterized by a high-resolution micro-focus computed tomography (μCT) system (V|tome|x M300, GE Sensing & Inspection Technology) at PontLab (Pontedera, Pisa, Italy), whose scan parameters are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2 - Summary of μ CT scan parameters

CT Scan parameters	Values
<i>Voltage/current</i>	140 kV / 180 μ A
<i>Filters</i>	No filters
<i>Focus-to-Object Distance (FOD) - Focus-to-Detector Distance (FDD)</i>	100.000 - 808.385 mm
<i>Voxel size</i>	24.74 μ m
<i>Exposure time</i>	250 ms
<i>Averaging/Skip</i>	1/0
<i>Sensitivity</i>	0.3
<i>Number of images</i>	2200

To maximize the resolution of the μ CT analysis, the inspected region was limited only to the external borders of a representative face. In this manner, a resolution with a voxel size of 24.74 μ m was reached, as detailed in **Table 2**.

2.2 Definition of the optimal MW-CVI loaded reactor configuration

The MW heating of samples with large surfaces and volumes is demanding from different points of view. The net MW power necessary to keep the whole SiC_f/SiC tube surface at a uniform temperature of 900°C is necessarily high, of the order of 5 kW¹ for the considered case, as estimated by the Stefan-Boltzmann law for unitary emissivity [42].

In addition to the high power, the temperature distributions are likely to be scarcely homogeneous. This nonuniform heating can be exacerbated for dielectric losses that strongly increase with the temperature. Indeed, in this case, a mutual reinforcement mechanism is established between dielectric loss and temperature increase, leading to randomly distributed hot spots over the sample surface.

To avoid the uncontrollable occurrence of hot spots, the preparation of the MW-CVI trials required:

- 1) Development of a specific arrangement of the sample in the reactor, optimizing the energy efficiency and enabling a monitoring of the temperature distribution on the largest possible surface of the CMC preform;

¹ Given by the net microwave power dissipated in the sample excluding the unavoidable losses in the reactor walls.

- 2) Setup of the MW heating parameters for a homogeneous sample heating and well-defined thru-thickness temperature gradients resulting in a controlled SiC matrix densification front [46];

The first point was addressed by the development of a dedicated quartz-based sample holder, manufactured by welding together rods of high-purity quartz (Momentive 214), with a chair-like structure where the CMC sample can be placed with a vertical orientation, as displayed in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1 - Upper view of the inner graphite cavity showing the configuration employed during the MW-CVI trials for SiC_f/SiC-C2 infiltration (Left) and frontal view of the sample (Right)

Moreover, to avoid the formation of hotspots localized in the regions of contact between the SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample and the sample holder, a layered SiC-fiber reinforced preform was interposed (**Figure 1 - Left**). It consists of three stacked 10 cm x 10 cm Hi-Nicalon Type S fabrics, which were knitted together with a cotton yarn and whose edges were coated with the same SiC-based slurry employed for the CMC tube. The much smaller volume of this component with respect to the bulky SiC_f/SiC-C2 tube is expected to affect only marginally the process energy efficiency.

During the first MW-CVI trials, it was also necessary to include a cylindrical mullite-based refractory (Altraform KVS 184-400 - Rath group GmbH, Germany) in the setup to improve the heating pattern uniformity, which was limited by the high starting values of the CMC preform complex permittivity (see **Table 1a** in the Appendix). The selection of this material grade, suggested by its low dielectric losses and thermal properties, was supported by the experience in the MW-assisted sintering of nuclear ceramics up to 1800°C [47].

The refractory cylinder, having a 6 cm diameter and 12.7 cm length, was placed on the sample holder coaxially to the CMC tube. It helped to minimize the radiative heat losses from the internal sample surface and to limit the occurrence of hot spots. The refractory diameter was selected to improve the temperature uniformity of the CMC sample at infiltration conditions, while still keeping

its surface temperature sufficiently low. In this manner, the deposition of the SiC matrix on the surface of the refractory, which could result in a decrease of the process chemical and energy efficiencies, can be avoided.

The frontal sample surface temperature profile was monitored using three high-resolution thermal cameras (Optris PI 1M – Optris GmbH, Berlin, Germany), according to the scheme described in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 - MW-CVI loaded reactor configuration and thermal cameras setup for the temperature profile monitoring of the large CMC tubular sample

The implemented configuration enabled the monitoring of the temperature distribution of a large part of the sample surface. For the considered CMC sample dimensions, 75% of the overall SiC_f/SiC-C2 surface can be monitored.

For the setup of the MW heating parameters, the numerical multiphysics modeling of the reactor, specifically developed to investigate the multiport and multifrequency excitation of the system on the basis of the Comsol Multiphysics 6.2 software [43,48], played a role of paramount importance. Its goal was first to achieve a good temperature uniformity across the large sample considered, possibly paving the way to expand the MW-assisted chemical processes beyond lab-scale applications. Moreover, the possibility of spreading the requested MW power among the three excitation channels (multiport) was expected to decrease the occurrence of plasma due to the lower energy density in the reactor. The wide availability of EM modes characterizing an overmoded reactor was exploited for a smart multifrequency excitation of the loaded MW-CVI reactor, which resulted in a higher electric field homogeneity on the CMC sample. At the same time, it brought a reduced risk of unwanted coupling between different channels (cross-coupling), avoiding a decrease in the process energy

efficiency. The values of the dielectric, thermal, and emissivity properties, employed in the numerical modeling, are reported in the Appendix.

The numerical analysis of the EM behavior of the loaded MW-CVI reactor consisted of a frequency domain study, using the “RF Module”, in the ISM 2.4 – 2.5 GHz range by single port excitation. The analysis of the distribution of the amplitude of the electric field (or of the EM losses) in the sample revealed the most relevant EM mode(s), on the basis of their uniformity inside the sample and their energy efficiency. A convenient approach to assess the quality of the resonance modes, independently of the position of the stub tuners, is to calculate the energy efficiency of the mode, in which the energy efficiency is defined as the ratio of the MW power dissipated in the entire sample region P_s , to the MW power entering in the reactor P through the excitation port.

The solution of the coupled EM - Thermal problem, required for the MW heating modelling, was computed using the “RF Module” and “Heat Transfer Module” of COMSOL software. These two modules interact, with parameters from one influencing the other. Specifically, the MW power P_s generated through dielectric absorption acts as a heat source within the CMC sample. Conversely, the local temperature of the sample affects its dielectric permittivity, as well as other temperature-dependent properties.

The two problems are solved in a self-consistent way. Heat transfer equations are applied only within the sample, while the surrounding environment is accounted for through thermal radiation. This radiation is modelled as being directed toward the cold reactor walls, which are assumed to remain at room temperature. In practical applications, the temperature of the reactor walls during the infiltration process remains significantly lower than the infiltration temperature, thus their contribution to the Stefan-Boltzmann law is considered negligible. Conductive and convective heat losses are also neglected due to their minimal contribution with respect to the radiative losses. This simplification is justified by the low thermal conductivity of the quartz sample holder and the rarefied atmosphere condition during the infiltration.

The multifrequency excitation capability of the reactor was implemented within the multiphysics model. Specifically, multiple frequency domain modules were used, each configured with its own operating frequency and excitation port. These were coupled with a single thermal module, whereas the heat source was given by the EM losses in the sample at the three excitation frequencies. Finally, as was done for the single-port excitation case, all four problems were solved simultaneously and in a self-consistent way.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Electromagnetic-Thermal assessment of the loaded MW-CVI reactor

At first, the MW heating efficiency was determined from the related power spectrum. The resulting energy efficiency vs frequency curves are plotted in **Figure 3** for each excitation channel.

Figure 3 – Numerical energy efficiency vs frequency spectra of the loaded cavity excited by single-port excitation by SSG1, SSG2, SSG3, according to the scheme described in **Figure 2**

The EM spectra of the loaded MW-CVI reactor depend only to a small extent on the excitation port, as expected from the cylindrical symmetry of the CMC sample. Small residual differences among the curves of **Figure 3** are ascribed to the sample holder, whose geometry did not match the symmetry of the cavity. As a result, the identification of the optimal operating frequencies in the EM models can be basically obtained from each of the single-port excitation cases. Secondly, the spectra are characterized by broad resonances, suggesting a quite stable frequency behaviour during the MW-CVI process. Finally, a high energy efficiency, reaching values of about 90%, is expected for the MW heating of the large SiC_f/SiC tube of interest.

The solution provided by the EM-Thermal models corroborated the initial difficulties in efficiently heating the tubular-shaped CMC preform. **Figure 4** displays some characteristic views of the computed temperature pattern of the sample, obtained at the same experimental conditions reported in **Table 3**. They are characterized by quite localized heating at the bottom and top edges, and only limited portions of the sample reached temperature values high enough for the SiC matrix infiltration process.

Figure 4 - Characteristic views of the numerical temperature distribution [°C] of the tubular-shaped SiC_f/SiC preform by Multiport-Multifrequency excitation according to the parameters reported in **Table 3**

Table 3 – MW heating parameters of the tubular-shaped SiC_f/SiC sample employed during the first 6.5 h of MW-CVI process

Numerical model MW heating parameters – First 6.5 h of MW-CVI process		
Excitation channel	Average operating frequency [MHz]	Average MW Transmitted power [kW]
Channel 1	2472	1.24
Channel 2	2486	1.37
Channel 3	2452	1.21

However, after 50 hours of MW-CVI process, the CMC tube heating pattern resulted to be greatly improved. The resulting temperature profiles, obtained from the multiport-multifrequency modelling, at an advanced densification level, are displayed in **Figure 5**. The MW heating parameters of the model, reported in **Table 4**, corresponded to those employed during the experimental trials.

Figure 5 - Characteristic views of the numerical temperature distribution [°C] of the tubular-shaped SiC_f/SiC preform by Multiport-Multifrequency excitation according to the parameters reported in **Table 4**

Table 4 - MW heating parameters of the tubular-shaped SiC_f/SiC sample employed from 6.5 h until 50 h of MW-CVI process

Numerical model MW heating parameters – From 6.5 h until 50 h of MW-CVI process		
<i>Excitation channel</i>	<i>Average operating frequency [MHz]</i>	<i>Average MW Transmitted power [kW]</i>
Channel 1	2483	1.70
Channel 2	2484	1.66
Channel 3	2479	1.37

According to **Figure 5**, a remarkable increase in the heating pattern uniformity was obtained thanks to the more favourable dielectric properties of the CMC sample, at a higher density level, in turn due to the increased SiC matrix content.

3.2 Results of the experimental MW-CVI trials

SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample underwent a 50 h infiltration cycle at an operating pressure of 200 mbar and a maximum temperature of about 893°C, under a H₂+MTS reagents mixture with a 10:1 molar ratio. Before each MW-CVI process run, the loaded reactor was thoroughly dried at 200°C for 2 hours by conventional heating at a pressure of 25 mbar. The leak tightness of the system was verified, considering acceptable a maximum pressure increase of 1 mbar every 10 min.

Single-port excitation tests, performed at operating frequencies according to the EM-Thermal modelling results, were carried out to determine the optimal frequency combination for the experimental trials. The MW power coupling levels were adjusted by means of the stubs mounted on the excitation channels. Final adjustments in the MW frequencies were made on the basis of the observed temperature pattern. Finally, multiport-multifrequency tests were performed to set the MW power according to the needed infiltration temperature, controlling and possibly adjusting the cross-coupling levels.

Despite the presence of the refractory, the first MW-CVI trials evidenced significant difficulties in heating the SiC_f/SiC sample up to the infiltration temperature. Indeed, only localized sample regions reached the target temperature, as expected from the numerical modelling results described in *Section 3.1*, limiting the deposition of the SiC matrix and thus of the process chemical efficiency. An example is given in **Figure 6**, where only the temperature patterns from Channels 1 and 2 are

reported since no temperature points, above the lower temperature reading value of the thermal camera of 595°C, were visible from Channel 3.

Figure 6 – Starting SiC_f/SiC tube temperature profiles from Channel 1 (Left) and Channel 2 (Right) using the mullite-based refractory

Moreover, the mullite-based refractory reacted unexpectedly within the MTS/H₂ environment. It is known from literature that mullite, as well as other silica (SiO₂) based refractories, react with hydrogen at temperatures of about 1400°C, according to **Equation 1** [49]:

However, according to the numerical modelling results, during the MW-CVI process trials, the temperature of the refractory was expected to be about 90°C lower than the CMC sample surface, thus quite below the temperature necessary to activate the reaction of **Equation 1**. Since any plasma formation was observed during the tests, it was postulated that the MW heating might have intensified the kinetics of **Equation 1**, resulting in a lower activation temperature. Anyway, the concomitant interaction of the refractory with the MTS/H₂ environment was very problematic due to the consequent reaction among the released H₂O_(g) with the MTS, resulting in SiO₂ formation in the reactor. The latter reaction is not only detrimental to the process efficiency but also to the rapid contamination of the reactor and shadowing of the quartz windows, thus impeding the control of the CMC sample temperature profile.

Still, due to the limited heating pattern uniformity, the presence of the refractory was initially deemed necessary. The employed reactor configuration forced to daily MW-CVI runs with durations among 30 to 90 minutes, to avoid the occurrence of the reaction described in **Equation 1**.

Along the different infiltration runs, the extension of the sample region above the infiltration temperature steadily increased. After 6.5 hours of MW-CVI processing, corresponding to the SiC_f/SiC tube weight increase (i.e. SiC matrix increase) of 3.26 g (i.e. 1.32 %vol SiC matrix content), the higher SiC matrix content the heating pattern without the refractory, shown in **Figure 7**, became similar to the starting temperature pattern (**Figure 6**), obtained with the refractory. Thus, the

subsequent infiltration trials, each longer than 90 minutes, were conducted without the refractory, collecting a total of 50 hours of infiltration process.

Figure 7 - SiC_f/SiC tube temperature profiles from Channel 1 (Left) and Channel 2 (Right) without the refractory after 6.5 h of MW-CVI processing

The final weight increase of the infiltrated CMC tube was of additional 31.33 g (i.e. 14.01 %vol SiC matrix content). The relative density evolution (target density of 2.4 g/cm³) of the CMC tube is reported in **Figure 8**, which shows the two different densification stages with and without the refractory.

Figure 8 - SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample relative density evolution during the MW-CVI process

The CMC tube density increase resulted in a remarkable improvement of the sample heating pattern uniformity, as clearly shown in **Figure 9**. The observed temperature distribution well corresponds to that predicted by the numerical modelling (see *Section 3.1*), characterized by wide central regions of the SiC_f/SiC tube homogeneously heated within the infiltration temperature range.

Figure 9 - SiC/SiC tube temperature profiles from Channel 1 (Left), Channel 2 (Middle), and Channel 3 (Right) without the refractory after 50 h of MW-CVI processing

The CMC tube heating pattern highlighted in **Figure 9** is the proof demonstrating that the $\lambda_{MW/4}$ barrier in the MW heating of large samples can be lifted, combining a specific, accurate EM reactor modelling and design, with a flexible MW source and excitation system, capable to adapt to the variable EM spectrum of the reactor. The homogeneous heating of the sample translated into an increase of the SiC matrix deposition rates, as reported in **Figure 10**.

Figure 10 - Deposition rates with processing time during the various MW-CVI trials

Based on the data reported in **Figure 10**, a total average deposition rate of 0.76 g/h was computed only during the more meaningful tests carried out without the refractory. Still, a well-defined trend of the deposition rate evolution during the MW-CVI process was not observed due to the different heating conditions among different tests. Indeed, every 6-8 hours of densification, the CMC tube was rotated by about 90° around its axis, replacing denser parts of the sample with lower-density ones. Despite this, the EM mode distributions were not significantly changed after each turn, i.e. electric field pattern did not critically depend on the density distribution in the CMC sample. However, after the sample rotation, the new regions involved in the MW-CVI process, characterized by a lower SiC

matrix content and thus lower dielectric losses, exhibited lower heating pattern uniformities, affecting the deposition rate.

For the determination of the overall energy efficiency of the employed multiport configuration, an important aspect is the cross-coupling level between the excitation channels. In the investigated case of SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample trials, typical values of the total cross-coupling level lower than 11.2 % were obtained, lower than the values reported in a previous study conducted with the same reactor [43]. Such a low value of the cross-coupling is partially due to the use of different MW frequencies for the various excitation channels, demonstrating the importance of using a frequency-tunable MW source system. Finally, despite the higher power levels needed for the MW heating of the large tubular sample, no plasma formation was noted during the infiltration session, confirming the benefits of the employed multiport-multifrequency approach.

As regards the reactor performance, in the absence of the refractory, it was possible to perform overall MW-CVI runs of about 8 hours, split among three different days, without the need to open the reactor. It was not possible to carry out daily runs longer than 3.5 hours due to the rise of the temperature of the reactor chamber walls, as a consequence of the CMC thermal irradiation and of the unavoidable EM losses in the reactor walls. The rise in the temperature of the reactor walls was also due to the lack of an active cooling system of the reactor. For safety reasons, the maximum temperature that was considered acceptable for the internal graphite walls of the reactor was 450 °C.

Finally, the SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample densification and residual porosity levels were evaluated through μ CT analysis after the MW-CVI process (see **Figure 11**).

Figure 11 - Rendering of the reconstructed SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample volume (Left); analysed regions of a representative CMC sample face after 50 h of MW-CVI process (Right)

The respective porosity of six 10 mm x10 mm square regions, shown in **Figure 11 – Right**, were determined. The related values are reported in **Table 5**.

Table 5 - Porosity measurements by μ CT analysis after the MW-CVI process (the reference regions are indicated in **Figure 11**)

Area	Porosity [%vol]
Region #1	24
Region #3	14
Region #9	23
Region #10	25
Region #11	25
Region #12	18

These porosity values differed by about 25-35 %vol with respect to the starting value determined by Archimedes measurement, as a result of the increased SiC matrix content in the preform, thus confirming a good and quite homogeneous reduction of the SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample porosity.

The analysis of the CMC tube regions micrographs along the thickness, displayed in **Figure 12**, confirmed the achievement of a controlled densification front without any crusting that might limit the further access of the gaseous reagents for the infiltration tests prosecution.

Figure 12 - μ CT scans of the SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample regions (Region 1 and 3), analysed along the thickness after the MW-CVI process

Differently from the CMC square-shaped samples treated in previous work [43], characterized by the peculiar inside-out densification front derived from the inverse temperature profile in the material, during the trials with the CMC tube, the SiC matrix infiltration progressed from the inner to the outer tube surface. The latter result is a consequence of the lower thermal irradiation of the internal curved surfaces of the CMC, leading to a maximum surface-to-core temperature difference of about 30°C, computed by the solution of the numerical models described in *Sect. 3.1*.

The remarkable contribution of the μ CT analysis provides further confirmation of the performance of the MW-CVI technology for the densification of large SiC-based CMCs with tubular geometry with respect to other conventional CMCs manufacturing routes.

4. Conclusions

Electrification of industrial processes is increasingly gaining attention due to the urgent need to mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions while keeping good process yields and product quality. In this framework, MW-assisted processes are playing a growing role in material synthesis and process intensification. However, these processes face significant scalability challenges, especially at high temperatures, primarily due to issues related to uniform heating as a consequence of the so-called $\lambda_{MW}/4$ barrier. Addressing these challenges is crucial to unleash the potential of the MW-assisted processes.

In this work, a large SiC_f/SiC CMC tube was successfully densified in an innovative MW-CVI pilot plant, overcoming the conventional limitations on the sample dimension, through an efficient combination of overmoded resonant reactor design, multiport excitation scheme, tunable multifrequency excitation, and rigorous numerical modelling of the reactor in the operational configuration.

A key point of the proposed approach was represented by the overmoded resonant structure of the reactor, enabling the simultaneous excitation of several EM modes, potentially providing a more uniform heating pattern. The excitation of several modes was facilitated by the multiport configuration of the reactor, enabling three different access points for the MW power. A further benefit was represented by the use of different excitation frequencies, covering in principle the entire ISM band around 2.45 GHz. Indeed, the tunability of the MW source system provided a much larger freedom in the choice of the most suited modes, selected also to limit the cross-coupling among the excitation channels.

The link among the sample temperature and the several EM parameters involved in the process - the three frequencies and the three powers - was provided by the numerical modeling, which solved in a self-consistent way the EM and thermal equations with different excitation ports and frequencies, including the experimentally determined values of the dielectric, thermal, and emission properties of the sample as a function of the temperature.

The energy efficiency calculated for the reactor loaded by a tubular SiC_f/SiC sample with 10 cm external diameter, 12.7 cm height, and 0.3 cm thickness reached values as high as 90%.

The evolution of the sample temperature during the heating and infiltration stage was monitored by a three high-resolution thermal cameras system, providing an almost complete view of the CMC tube surface temperature, with a resolution better than a millimeter.

As a result of the infiltration runs, the SiC_f/SiC tube relative density increased from 58% to 77% after 50 hours, with an average SiC matrix deposition rate of 0.76 g/h, in good agreement with the

reduction of about one order of magnitude of the processing time expected for the MW-CVI in comparison to conventional CVI. X-ray computed tomography analyses confirmed the achievement of a controlled densification front, avoiding the crusting issue, and of a homogeneous porosity reduction, further corroborating the potential of this technique for the near-net-shape manufacturing of large tubular SiC-based CMC samples with respect to conventional routes.

In conclusion, the results reported in this paper demonstrate, for the first time to our knowledge, that the scalability issue of the MW-assisted processes can be effectively overcome, paving the way to applications at an industrial level and to the full maturity of this technique.

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Data Availability Statement

Data can be made available upon request to the authors.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix

The dielectric and thermal properties of the SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample, employed in the Electromagnetic (EM) - Thermal models of *Sect. 3.1*, are reported in **Tables 1a** to **5a**. The dielectric permittivity and the total normal emissivity were measured as part of the activities described in previous works [42,43], while the thermal conductivity and the specific heat were measured by Petroceramics (<http://www.petroceramics.com/>) during a previous project.

Table 1a – Real and imaginary part of the dielectric permittivity values as a function of the temperature for SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample at a density of 1.39 g/cm³

T [°C]	ϵ'_r	ϵ''_r
25	28.48	22.02
100	29.10	23.56
200	31.67	26.05
300	34.67	28.73
400	37.34	31.18
500	40.83	33.46
600	45.84	36.00
700	51.12	37.96
800	55.74	39.65
900	58.56	39.63
1000	58.39	38.11

Table 2a – Real and imaginary part of the dielectric permittivity values as a function of the temperature for SiC_f/SiC-C2 sample at a density of 1.91 g/cm³

T [°C]	ϵ'_r	ϵ''_r
25	7.37	3.51
100	7.84	3.70
200	8.77	4.21
300	9.64	4.73
400	10.64	5.15
500	12.33	6.08
700	16.03	7.52

800	16.71	8.90
900	16.50	9.01

Table 3a – Total normal emissivity (ϵ_{tot}) as a function of the temperature

T [°C]	ϵ_{tot}
19.85	0.690
112.85	0.700
200.85	0.710
337.85	0.730
462.85	0.750
566.85	0.880
623.85	0.884
705.85	0.888
807.85	0.872
944.85	0.834
1124.85	0.823

Table 4a – Thermal conductivity (λ) values as a function of the temperature

T [°C]	λ [$W/(m * K)$]
25	0.67
200	0.78
400	0.80
600	0.83
800	1.00
1000	1.21

Table 5a – Specific heat (c_p) as a function of the temperature

T [°C]	c_p [$J/(kg * K)$]
25	710
200	1000
400	1190

600	1340
800	1570
1000	1870

For all the above quantities, a linear function was employed both for the interpolation between consecutive points and for the extrapolation outside the measurement intervals.